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DOLPHIN AS A PSYCHOPOMP: A WINDOW INTO THE PSYCHO-SPACE OF CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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Young children between two and seven years of age, during the so-called pre-operational stage of their cognitive development, often demonstrate a lack of the capacity to appreciate a perspective different from their own. This mental stance has been termed as egocentrism. Egocentrism must not be confused with egoism or egotism – both are referring to an excessive or exaggerated sense of self-importance of an individual, who is often motivated by self-interest and may or may not be done at the expense of others.

The late Jean Piaget (1896-1980), a renowned Swiss development psychologist, has defined egocentrism as an incomplete differentiation of the Self and the world at large, including other people (we have chosen to shorten the phrase and termed it as Otherselves, i.e., other Selves besides the Self), with the tendency to perceive, comprehend and interpret the surrounding world in terms of Self. In other words, these young children do not possess the mental capacity to comprehend that other people may hold viewpoints different from theirs. They tend to select their own viewpoint of what they see rather than the actual viewpoint shown to others (Santrock, 2008).

When a child is deeply egocentric, he/she becomes “blind” to others or his/her peers. In such an instance, the child is said to manifest two main difficulties in (i) being able to attribute mental states to others as a natural way of understanding them (also known as the theory of mind); and (ii) having an automatic appropriate emotional reaction to others' mental states. These difficulties hamper successful social interaction resulting in a major failure in empathizing, which is also known as mentalizing. Such a condition is described as hyper-egocentrism, which is one of the key symptoms observed in individuals with autism.

Along with egocentrism is the other mental stance known as animism, i.e., the belief that inanimate objects are capable of actions and have life-like traits. One good example is that young children do believe toys – as depicted in the Walt Disney movie of the Toy Story – are real and alive except that they do not show it, especially when there are human adults around. In child psychology, Jean Piaget has referred the term to an implicit comprehension of the world in a child's mind that assumes all events are the product of intention or consciousness. This is cognitive immaturity (and hence,

inability and NOT disability) to distinguish the external world from one's own psyche. Developmental psychology has since established that the distinction of animate versus inanimate things is an abstraction acquired by learning.

When egocentrism and animism come into play together, they project a very powerful mental stance termed as magical thinking. This is used to describe causal reasoning that seeks correlation, which can be either possible but improbable or probable but impossible, between acts or utterances and certain events. The first one deals with a meta-world of improbabilities (i.e., not likely but can possibly happen) and the other, a meta-world of impossibilities (i.e., not possible and can never happen). On the one hand, the meta-world of improbabilities includes Conan Doyle's Lost World and James Cameron's Pandora – the planet where the Na'vi tribe dwells – in the blockbuster movie Avatar. On the other hand, the meta-world of impossibilities such as Lewis Carroll's Wonderland and Frank Baum's Land of Oz, where anything can happen at any time has no premises to condition the rest of the story. In this other meta-world of fantasy, carpets fly, a frog turns into a handsome prince, a rabbit carries a watch in its waistcoat pocket, a witch flies on her broomstick ... There are no maxims, physical or moral, to govern this meta-world. It is an amoral polymorphous world of a naïve child. These meta-worlds are invented worlds and collectively we have termed them as psycho-space, which exists only in our mind of imaginations. Therefore, it is not surprising to note that many young children are unable to differentiate between what is real and what is not.

CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

According to Chia (2008), ASD is “a neuro-developmental syndrome of constitutional origin (genetic) and whose cause could also be epigenetic, and its onset is usually around first three years of birth, with empathizing or mentalizing deficits that result in a triad of impairments in communication, social interaction, and imagination (or presence of stereotyped behaviors), but may, on the other hand, display (especially by autistic savants) or hide (especially by autistic crypto-savants) a strong systemizing drive that accounts for a distinct triad of strengths in good attention to detail, deep narrow

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interests, and islets of ability” (p.10).

As mentioned earlier, children and adolescents with ASD manifest hyper-egocentrism. This has caused them to appear aloof and isolated – living in the world (or meta-world) of their own. To bring a child or adolescent with ASD out of that world of hyper-egocentrism, we need to know the portal or channel to enter that meta-world. However, it becomes a mission impossible if we have no idea how to get into that world or meta-world. We need someone or something to show us the way. That someone or something is what is termed as a psychopomp. For an example, the wardrobe in the book *The Lion, the Witch and the Wardrobe*, written by C.S. Lewis, serves as some kind of a portal to the imaginary land of Narnia, a world that exists parallel to ours, allowing four English children to cross over to that meta-world from here. The wardrobe is a psychopomp. In another example, the rabbit with a watch in its waistcoat pocket in a hurry rushing to somewhere and Alice following it into a tree-hole that took her to the meta-world of Wonderland. Both the rabbit and the tree-hole are psychopomps. Finally, in our last example here, the body of an avatar that Jake Scully, a crippled marine, has to enter in order to stay in touch with the natives of the Na'vi tribe in James Cameron's blockbuster movie *Avatar*, is a psychopomp.

We need a psychopomp to enter into the world of a child or adolescent with ASD. We have to look for one. This approach is certainly going to be very different from the conventional intervention approaches such as the Applied Behaviour Analysis and the Greenspan floortime plan that are commonly used when treating individuals with autism. We did not have to look far. We found our psychopomp. The pink dolphins (known as indo-pacific humpback dolphins) at the Dolphin Lagoon in Sentosa, would become our psychopomp(s).

Dolphin-assisted therapy

There has always been something special about the dolphins. To the Minoans as far back as 1500 BCE, dolphins are symbols of joy and music. The ancient Greeks even dedicated a temple at Delphi to a dolphin god. This special relationship between humans and dolphins has gone beyond just religious belief, moving into scientific and medical domains.

In the early 1970s, dolphins have been the subjects of interests in research investigation relating to the understanding of effects of dolphin-human interaction on human behavior. Dolphins have been trained to assist individuals with disabilities, and this form of intervention approach became popularly known as dolphin-assisted therapy (DAT). Several experimental studies have been done to investigate the effectiveness of DAT with children with various disabilities, mental retardation, and autism. One study reported how autistic children were relieved of their characteristic anxiety (e.g., vocal and motor self-stimulations and rocking movement) and stress through

positive interactions with dolphins, and subsequently they also improved in their communication and learning. Another study reported that DAT helped to motivate an autistic child to communicate. In Singapore, one study was reported in 2009 on the efficacy of DAT on reduction of stereotyped behavior in non-verbal children with ASD and these subjects also began to hand-signal in their attempt to communicate with others.

There are many different forms of DAT. The simplest form can involve a child swimming with, touching or taking care of dolphins, while the more complex one is based on an individualized structured program designed to meet the needs of the child concerned. According to Nathanson (1998), the DAT is based on the theory that children with disabilities will increase their attention to relevant stimuli in the environment as a result of their desire to interact with dolphins. The general purpose of DAT is to encourage children with disabilities to engage in desired responses in accordance with their individual education or therapy plan.

HOW DOLPHIN-ASSISTED THERAPY HAS PROMOTED AWARENESS IN AUTISTIC CHILDREN

For past three years since end of 2007, we have been researching on the efficacy of short-term (i.e., a duration of between three and six months) DAT for children and adolescents with ASD, looking for new discoveries that we might have missed previously. With parental consent, five autistic children aged between five and seven years old participated as subjects in the Dolphin Encounter for Special Children (DESC) program – a short-term dolphin-assisted therapy offered by the Underwater World Singapore, and being conducted by qualified therapists and dolphin trainers at the Dolphin Lagoon in Sentosa, an island south of mainland Singapore.

Over three months and on every Wednesday for almost an hour, these children learnt to keep their eyes on the dolphin as it swam around the pool, use hand signals to initiate a certain response from the dolphin (i.e., performing what we would call dolphin tricks such as waving goodbye to the dolphin which would respond by waving one of its flippers back, holding and shaking the flippers like a friendly handshake), pat on the dolphin when it came forward to them, feed the dolphin, waddle in the water with the dolphin swimming around them, and for the more daring ones, even swam with the dolphin in the pool.

What we have noticed in the major behavioral change of these children with ASD is the reduction in their hyper-egocentrism. They have also become more socially aware of themselves, beginning with the somatic awareness of their hands (e.g., performing a hand signal to get the dolphin to respond back) and legs (e.g., waddling their legs in the pool). No longer did they have to hold someone's arms using them as if they were a tool to get something or to do something. These children could do proto-declarative

pointing if they wanted something (e.g., pointing to the dolphin, keeping an eye contact with it and beckoning it to come forward). The somatic awareness led them to what we have termed “decentrizing” their hyper-egocentrism. To decentrize is to break down the walls of hyper-egocentrism, leaving the egocentrism without the hyper part.

At the beginning of DAT, the dolphin was like some sort of an awareness initiator to these children a point of a social contact. Along the way, during the process of DAT and over a period of time, the dolphin became an awareness mediator between the child and his/her surrounding (superimposed with the dolphin = child, and its pool = child's surrounding). By the end of third month, these children became very aware of the surrounding, that is, the dolphin pool with at least one dolphin swimming in it at any one time. The dolphin pool is like a photo-frame encapsulating the dolphin within it. It can represent the psycho-space in the mind of a child: simple and clear, without any other distractions. It has its unique hypnotic effect on the child's mind. The dolphin now plays the role of an awareness reinforcer in these children. From the somatic awareness, these children have developed a psycho-spatial awareness that is gradually transformed into their environmental awareness. The discussion on how this transformational process takes place is beyond the scope of this paper. This transformation has been our greatest breakthrough in our DAT research. Not only did these children become environmentally more aware than before, they became socially aware of themselves and the people, especially their parents and siblings around them, too. They could now aware, i.e., taking a deliberate choice to make awareness. We have termed this transformational process aware (i.e., to aware is an action rather than to be aware of, a passive reaction). By this term, we mean transforming of awareness to be integrated into the new mental schemes so as to take into account the particularities of the objects, persons, or events the child is interacting with.

In Piagetian terms, we would refer the process of aware to assimilation and accommodation the two basic functions in the process of understanding (making sense) that is the basic mechanism of ensuring equilibrium in the relationship between the child and his/her environment. The environment is assimilated into the schemes of perception and actions that are already available or existing in the child's mind. These schemes are transformed or accommodated to the peculiarities of the objects (e.g., the dolphin) of the environment (e.g., the dolphin pool), if they are not completely appropriate. Hence, the cognitive development is a continuous process of assimilations and accommodations that lead to increasing expansion in the application of and coordination between schemes, enhancing internalization of schemes, and developing an abstraction of them. These are mental operations that are

gradually coordinated with each other, generating new structures of mental operations that are applied on representations of objects rather than on the objects themselves. Mental images, words and numerical notations are good representations standing for objects and hence, each of them becomes the object of mental operations.

We have summarized our research into the following diagram below:

For those of us who have come very close in our encounter with dolphins, we have experienced a warm feeling, unexplained by words alone, and what exactly it is we are unable to describe. It still remains a big mystery. To quote from Dr Horace Dobbs (1990), the founding director of the International Dolphin Watch, “[F]or want of a better word, let us call it the spirit of the dolphin” (p.15).

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